

Kinetics and Mechanisms of Ligand Exchange Reactions : A Review

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Chemical reactions in which the composition of the first coordination sphere around a metal centre changes, are termed ligand exchange reactions. A thorough appreciation of the chemistry of transition metals requires an understanding and knowledge of their reaction mechanisms. In this review we discuss the salient features of exchange reactions under the following heads and sub heads: (i) Classification of substitution reactions (ii) Formation reactions, (iii) Dissociation reactions and (iv) Ligand displacement reactions: (a) monodentate ligand exchange reactions, (b) multidentate ligand exchange reactions, (c) metal exchange reactions between ligands, (d) double exchange reactions.

In the ensuing text further sub-division has been found necessary. While the discussion covers the principles governing the behaviour of transition metals in general, the emphasis is mainly laid on nickel(II), iron(II) and iron(III) metal centres.

In the context of coordination chemistry 'ligand exchange' embraces the replacement of ligand coordinated to a metal ion by a free ligand or replacement of the coordinated metal ion by a free metal ion in solution. The substitution process permeates the whole realm of coordination chemistry. A knowledge of the kinetics of substitution can be helpful in devising the best conditions for synthetic routes for preparing new metal complexes and to improve upon the older methods in addition to refining analytical procedures based on coordination chemistry^{1,2}. In the past two decades several excellent reviews³⁻⁶ and monographs⁷⁻⁹ have appeared on the mechanisms of inorganic reactions and a significant drive has been made towards visualising the nature of a variety of intermediates and transition states generated during reaction pathways.

Classification of substitution reactions

The terminology developed by Hughes and Ingold¹⁰ for organic reactions has been extended to the substitution reactions in coordination chemistry and two broader classifications, viz. nucleophilic substitution (ligand substitution) and electrophilic substitution (metal substitution) for these reactions arise. Another classification, due to Langford and Gray¹¹, anticipates three mechanistic classes of heterolytic substitution reactions in solution, viz. a dissociative (*D*) or S_N1 reaction (Hughes and Ingold) in which the leaving ligand is lost in the first step, producing an intermediate of reduced coordination number, an associative (*A*) or S_N2 reaction in which the entering ligand adds in the first step producing an intermediate of increased coordination number and lastly the concerted path called interchange (*I*). During interchange, the

leaving ligand moves from the inner to the outer coordination sphere while the entering ligand moves from the outer to the inner sphere. A reaction proceeding through interchange mechanism may have a variety of transition states of *A* and *D* reactions. Thus the interchange can be further subclassified into an associative activation or interchange (I_a) where the reaction rate is more sensitive to the variation of entering ligand rather than to variation of the leaving ligand and a dissociative activation or interchange (I_d) where the reaction rate is much more sensitive to the variation of the leaving ligand rather than that of the entering ligand. The a-d dichotomy appears to be the only convenient subdivision of the interchange process that is necessary for comprehensive discussion of ligand substitution processes. So the simplest notation designating both stoichiometric and intimate mechanism are *D*, I_d , *A* and I_a .

Excellent reviews on the subject especially covering substitution reactions on Ni^{II} ¹², Fe^{III} ¹³, Cd^{II} ¹⁴, Pd^{II} ^{14,15} and Mn^{III} ¹⁶ metal centres have been attempted in recent years by the workers from this laboratory and, therefore, only a brief description into the following broad headings is presented here.

Formation reactions

The formation of metal complexes takes place in media where usually water acts as a solvent. The rates of these reactions vary from very slow to very fast. A generally accepted mechanism for the complex formation was originally proposed by Eigen¹⁶. For complexes of monodentate ligands it involves the formation of an outer sphere complex between a solvated metal ion and the incoming ligand followed by loss of a solvent molecule from this

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outer sphere complex to give the desired species. The mechanism of formation of complexes from unidentate ligands can be extended to the formation of complexes of multidentate ligands with the minor modification that the ring closure may constitute the rate-determining step.

Dissociation reactions

The dissociation of metal complexes can be considered as the reverse of the complex formation. These reactions are, generally, much slower than the formation reactions. The mechanism proposed for the complex formation also accounts for the dissociation rates of complexes bearing unidentate, bidentate or ambidentate ligands. The rate constant depends upon opening of the chelate ring or sometimes rupture of penultimate metal-ligand bond. Both these situations have been encountered frequently with outgoing bidentate or multidentate ligand groups. The presence of an acid generally enhances the dissociation rate because protonation of the released ligand stabilises the intermediate relative to the fully coordinated form¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Ligand displacement reactions

Ligand substitution reactions of coordination compounds have been studied as intensively as any class of inorganic reactions. The kinetics of these processes have been investigated extensively for octahedral and to a lesser extent for square-planer complexes. A very wide span of rates is found ranging from extremely slow exchange of CN⁻ with NiCyDTA²⁻ (no evidence for formation of Ni(CN)₄²⁻ in 60 days)²⁰ to the almost diffusion-controlled exchange of H₂O between Cu(H₂O)₆²⁺ and water ($t_{1/2} = 10^{-8}$ s)²¹. Following are the four types of substitution reactions met with in coordination chemistry: (a) monodentate ligand exchange reactions, (b) multidentate ligand exchange reactions, (c) metal exchange reactions between ligands, and (d) double exchange reactions.

Monodentate ligand exchange reactions:

This section is concerned with the kinetics and mechanisms of substitution in complexes where monodentate ligands exchange with monodentate or multidentate ligands.

Monodentate by monodentate: The substitution of one monodentate ligand by another is the simplest case to consider and has been extensively used for investigating the mechanisms of substitution in many octahedral complexes as well as some square-planer complexes. The general reactions involve the replacement of a monodentate ligand present in the inner-coordination sphere in the solvent media.

There are two basic mechanisms for monodentate ligand exchange in aqueous solution. Considering the nickel-hexammine system, the first mechanism

would be a dissociative type,

The second would be a bimolecular mechanism involving water molecules,

It is difficult to distinguish between such mechanisms in aqueous solution. However, the lack of NH₃ attack on Ni(NH₃)₆²⁺ and the fact that a change of 30% in H₂O concentration produced no observable effect support a dissociative mechanism²².

The reactivity of low-spin iron(II) complexes with respect to substitution by monodentate ligands has received little attention in comparison with the large number of data available for other octahedral, low-spin complexes such as those of Co^{III}²³, Rh^{III}²⁴ and Ru^{II}^{24,25}. However, the kinetics and mechanisms of ligand replacements in pentacyano (ligand) ferrate(II), Fe(CN)₅L⁽³⁻ⁿ⁾⁻ complexes have been the subject of considerable interest in recent past, for several reasons. These low-spin iron species represent models for active sites in biological systems and the reactions with imidazole (ImidH) have been investigated in this regard²⁶. Another feature of these complexes is their use in redox reactions with metalloproteins²⁷.

The kinetics of substitution reactions of a series of complexes of the type Fe(CN)₅L⁽³⁻ⁿ⁾⁻ have been studied by Toma and Malin^{28,29} where L was an aromatic nitrogen heterocycle and the substituting ligand was N-methylpyrazinium ion (Mpz⁺). The rate of substitution varied with the nature of L and a saturation kinetics, typical of rate-determining loss of L from the complex, followed by rapid addition of the incoming ligand were inferred. This is the first study⁷ about monodentate ligand substitution reactions of simple low-spin Fe^{II} complexes which generally proceed by D or S_N1'lim mechanism according to following scheme (equation 5),

where m and n are charges on L and L₁ respectively.

A similar study³⁰ of the reaction of Fe(CN)₅SO₃²⁻ with CN⁻ has also been reported. Other examples include aquation of Fe(CN)₅NO³⁻³¹ and its reaction with ammonia, hydroxylamine or hydrazine³²; the reaction of Fe(CN)₅(3,5-Me₂-Py)³⁻

with CN^- , Pz and ImidH^{2+} , the reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5$, PhNO^{3-34} and of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{Py}^{3-35,36}$ with CN^- . Recently, Abu-Gharib *et al.*³⁷ reported the kinetic data for the reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(4\text{-CN-Py})^{3-}$ with a variety of incoming ligands over a range of concentrations in order to provide a good illustration of the saturation kinetics. Together with respective double reciprocal plots, these authors claim that these results are compatible with a limiting dissociative mechanism.

Malin *et al.*^{29,38} have observed that the intermediate $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ is quite insensitive to the nature and charge of the attacking reagent. In order to examine the influence of charges on the attacking reagents Bradic *et al.*³⁹ studied the kinetics of replacement with L^n being PhNO , 3-CN-Py, DMNA, SCN^- , CN^- and SO_3^{2-} , and the leaving ligand L^m being DMNA, PhNO , SO_3^{2-} and H_2O respectively. Finally, they concluded that the magnitudes of second order rate constant k_{L_1} are similar and vary with L^n in the range of 200–300, 40–60 and 3.3 $\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for neutral, singly and double-charged (SO_3^{2-}) anions respectively. Also, it has been shown that the greatest difference in rate constants is between Mpz^+ and SO_3^{2-} reacting with $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ for which $k_{\text{Mpz}^+}/k_{\text{SO}_3^{2-}}=167$. Limiting reaction rates, at sufficiently large concentrations of entering ligand L^n have been observed with all leaving ligands, except water where the replacement obeys a second order rate law^{49,58,59},

$$\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{L}_1^{(3-n)-}]}{dt} = k_{L_1}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3-}][\text{L}_1^n] \quad (6)$$

The photochemical reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}^{2-}$ with thiourea or diethylthiourea in methanol have also been studied and shown to follow a second order rate law⁴⁰. Several reports have appeared on the complex formation reactions involving $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3-}$ complex ion besides the discussion on the tendency of this ion to dimerise at higher concentration and the nature of the dimeric species⁴¹. Kinetic and thermodynamic data⁴²⁻⁴⁸ from mechanistic studies are consistent with a dissociative (*D*) mechanism involving the five coordinated intermediate $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ during the substitution process in these complexes.

In recent years, one of the diagnostic tests that is being widely applied for elucidating the substitution mechanisms, is the volume of activation ΔV^\ddagger ⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. Thus the most convincing evidence in favour of *D*-mechanism comes from the determination of ΔV^\ddagger . If the leaving group L^m is to dissociate completely in the transition state then a positive value of ΔV^\ddagger is interpreted as representing a stretching of a metal-ligand bond in the transition state and this favours a *D*-mechanism. The similarity in values of ΔV^\ddagger implies a common rate-determining step which does not involve the ligands (i.e. lack of dependence on the nature of the incoming ligand) while a positive sign suggests either a dissociative mechanism or a mechanism involving charge dispersal in the transition state⁵².

In the *D*-mechanism of the scheme given in equation (5), there is a competition between incoming ligand L^n and the outgoing ligand L^m for the transient intermediate $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ produced from $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{L}^{(3-m)-}$ which is characterised by the ratio of the second order rate constants k_{L_1}/k_L . This gives an idea of the reactivities of a variety of ligands for the intermediate $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$. Solvent effects on reactivity ratios k_{L_1}/k_L for the replacement of a ligand L^m by an incoming ligand L^n in the complexes of the type $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5-\text{L}^{(3-m)-}$ in aqueous solution at 25°. The relative reactivities of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ in various binary aqueous mixtures have also been discussed⁵³. Although both *D* and *I_a* mechanisms can explain equally well all the kinetic observations in aqueous solutions⁵⁰, a series of studies have been undertaken in mixed solvent in order to distinguish between *D* and *I_a* mechanisms^{37,50,52-56}. The decrease in rate with decreasing water concentration has been interpreted in terms of an *I_a* mechanism⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶.

Multidentate by monodentate : The displacement of multidentate ligands by monodentate ligands is another example of monodentate ligand exchange reactions. The cyanide is a potential monodentate ligand having the capacity of displacing multidentate ligands, viz. macrocyclic ligands, polyamines, polyaminocarboxylates and thioligands from their metal complexes. The reactions involving $\text{NiL}^{(n-2)-}$ complexes (L =macrocyclic ligand⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹, polyamines^{60,61} and polyaminocarboxylates^{20,62,63}) with cyanide ions have been studied extensively by many workers. Recently, Nigam *et al.* have investigated the kinetics and mechanisms for replacement of aminocarboxylates from mono(aminocarboxylato)hydroxoferrate(III) complexes by cyanide ions^{64,65}. The general mechanistic scheme for $\text{NiL}^{(n-2)-}-\text{CN}^-$ replacement reactions requires that three cyanides are bonded to nickel(II) ion while four cyanides are required in $\text{FeL}(\text{OH})^{(n-2)-}-\text{CN}^-$ systems (n =charge on ligand L) in their respective rate-determining steps. The last cyanide adds rapidly forming $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{OH}^{3-}$ as the case may be.

The $\text{FeL}(\text{OH})^{(n-2)-}-\text{CN}^-$ reaction presents some complications and takes place in three distinct stages^{64,65}. The mechanism for the first stage, i.e. the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{OH}^{3-}$ from $\text{FeL}(\text{OH})^{(n-2)-}$ complexes has already been reported for many aminocarboxylates as shown in equations (7)–(11),

where, L=HPDTA⁴⁻, HIDA²⁻, EDTA⁴⁻, HEDTA³⁻, DTPA⁶⁻, PDTA⁴⁻ and TTHA⁶⁻. The second stage of reaction is the conversion of Fe(CN)₅OH³⁻ to Fe(CN)₅³⁻ due to reaction with cyanide ions, present in excess, according to equation (12),

The third stage involves the oxidation of aminopolycarboxylates released in the first stage (equation 11) by Fe(CN)₅³⁻ formed in the second stage as shown in equation (13),

Very recently, we have carried out an independent detailed kinetic study of both the second and the third stage reactions, i.e. the reaction of Fe(CN)₅OH³⁻ with CN⁻ and the reaction of Fe(CN)₅³⁻ with TTHA⁶⁻ in order to obtain a better understanding of the whole reaction sequence⁶⁶.

Monodentate by multidentate : Reactions of this type have been studied extensively in connection with the replacement of coordinated water during the formation reactions of multidentate ligand complexes⁶. The reactions of open-chain and macrocyclic polyamines with Cu^{II} in strongly basic solutions have been studied⁶⁷ to examine the kinetic behaviour of the unprotonated ligands. Some kinetic information is also available on the reactions of Ni(CN)₄²⁻ with aminopolycarboxylate ligands. A mixed Ni(CN)₅L⁽ⁿ⁺¹⁾⁻ complex is formed before the rate determining step in which an additional CN⁻ is lost. The behaviour with trien is different, however, because the rate-determining step is the reaction of the ligand directly with Ni(CN)₄²⁻ by an associative mechanism⁶⁸. Also the disappearance of Ni(CN)₄²⁻ is greatly accelerated by the polyamine concentration in comparison to the much slower reaction of Ni(CN)₄²⁻ with aminocarboxylates^{20,69}. Crouse and Margerum⁶⁹ have reported the reaction of Ni(CN)₄²⁻ with a few polyamines in presence and absence of I₂ as a scavenger for cyanide ions. In presence of I₂ the released cyanide has no effect on the forward reaction rate but in absence of I₂ there is an inverse effect.

Multidentate ligand exchange reactions :

The majority of complexation reactions of metal ions involve chelation or multidentate coordination rather than monodentate substitution. These reactions involve displacement of one multidentate ligand by another from a metal ion complex and under favourable circumstances they can be very rapid. Their mechanisms depend on the coordinating

ability of both the ligands simultaneously and their classifications are cited in literature⁷⁰. The rate-determining step of the overall reaction is the cleavage of any one of the several bonds between metal and the leaving group which must be broken in the course of reaction. Multidentate ligand exchange kinetics of FeL (L=HEDTA and NTA) with PAR (4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol) have recently been studied in our laboratory⁷¹. Mentasti and Pelizzetti⁷² have investigated the kinetics of displacement of indicators (salicylic acid and tiron) complexed to Fe^{III} by EDTA. References to multidentate ligand exchange reactions on metal ions such as Zn^{II}⁷³, Cd^{II}⁷⁴, Hg^{II}⁷⁵, Cu^{II}^{73,76} and Ni^{II}⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ are available in literature. More recently, Kido and Hatakeyama have studied the multidentate ligand substitution reactions on Tc^{III} centre and found that Tc^{III} has got a lability very close to that of Cr^{III} and undergoes transformation via I_a-mechanism⁸¹.

Metal exchange reactions between ligands :

Multidentate ligand transfer between two metal ions, i.e. displacement of one metal cation from its complex with a multidentate ligand by another metal ion is represented by equation (14),

It has been proposed that the substitution proceeds through a dinuclear intermediate species, in which a multidentate ligand is partially bound to the entering metal ion, where the cleavage of one of the bonds between the ligand and the leaving metal ion constitutes the rate-determining step⁸². In some cases these reactions proceed via dissociation of initial complex with or without acid-catalysis followed by complex formation between the now free ligand and the displacing cations⁸³.

Most of the available data relate to the reactions of aminopolycarboxylato complexes⁸⁴, in particular the combination of various metal ions with EDTA, according to reaction (14)⁸⁵. Recently, a stopped-flow study of the reaction rate between copper(II) and polyaminocarboxylato complexes of cobalt(II) have been performed by Mentasti⁸² and evidence has been found for the stepwise unwrapping mechanism followed by attack of Cu^{II} to give a dinuclear intermediate for all the reactions.

Double exchange reactions :

An interesting situation exists when two multidentate complexes are mixed and the thermodynamics dictates a double exchange represented by equation (15),

The reactions of this category are generally slow because they proceed through cleavage of a series of coordinated bonds in succession^{86,87}. No evidence for the formation of a dicomplex intermediate has been reported so far but the rates of such reactions have been found to increase sharply if small amount of either a free ligand or a metal ion is added to the reaction mixture¹⁰⁸. The phenomenal

increase occurs due to operation of a coordination chain mechanism and has been used for analysis of traces of metals or ligands⁸⁷⁻⁹¹.

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